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4. Report:

Fixed bed reactor

Working principle

The fixed bed reactor uses electroactive denitrifying bacteria to remove nitrates from GW (Figure 1). A tubular reactor is set, with a central cathode compartment. The cathode is filled with granular electrodes, which work as a fixed conductive bed. Denitrifying bacteria grow on the granular electrode forming biofilm and using the electrode as the electron donor. The cathode is controlled at a poised cathode potential of -320 mV vs. Ag/AgCl for ensuring full NO_3^- conversion into N_2 , without NO_2^- nor N_2O accumulation (Pous et al., 2015). The cathode is separated from the anode by a tubular cation exchange membrane. Anodic biological oxidation of As(III) to As(V) was evaluated.

Figure 1: Working principle of the fixed-bed reactor.

Experimental / testing set-up

Table 1: Experimental set-up for test with Fixed bed reactor with anodic granular graphite.

Set-up	Fixed bed reactor with anodic granular graphite
Purpose of the study	Evaluate the simultaneous cathodic nitrate reduction and anodic arsenite oxidation
Description of the set-up	Two identical tubular BES. Anode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NAC = 0.15L. Anode/Cathode separator tubular CEM (CMI-7000, Membranes Int., USA). Cathode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NCC = 0.30L. Reference electrode: Ag/AgCl sat. KCl reference electrode (+0.197 V vs. SHE, SE 11, Xylem Analytics Germany). Cathode potential poised at -320 mV vs. Ag/AgCl.
Sampling	Influent and effluent
Analyzed parameters	NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , pH, conductivity (APHA, 2005). As(V) (ICS5000, Dionex, USA). Total arsenic by adding a strong oxidising agent (100 mM KMnO ₄). N ₂ O (Micosensor Unisense, Denmark).
Other observed parameters	Electrochemical characterization: CVs on sampled granules. Scan range = -600 - +200 mV vs. Ag/AgCl. Scan rate = 1mVs ⁻¹ .

Operation and results

Fixed bed reactor with anodic granular graphite

The removal of nitrates and arsenite was evaluated in the two tubular BES at different HRTs and recirculation flows as shown in Figure 2. Results obtained were published in Water Research journal (DOI: 10.1016/j.watres.2020.116748). The removal of nitrates increased by operating the systems at low hydraulic

retention times (HRTs) and by adjusting the recirculation flowrate (Figure 3). At 1.5 ± 0.1 HRT_{cathodic} and a recirculation flow-rate of $60 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$, nitrate was removed at a rate of $519 \pm 53 \text{ g N-NO}_3^- \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ NCC d}^{-1}$ ($2298 \pm 235 \text{ g NO}_3^- \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ NCC d}^{-1}$) ($90 \pm 6 \%$ removal) in reactor A and $456 \pm 61 \text{ g N-NO}_3^- \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ NCC d}^{-1}$ ($2019 \pm 270 \text{ g NO}_3^- \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ NCC d}^{-1}$) ($72 \pm 13 \%$ removal) in reactor B; without intermediates accumulation (no nitrite nor nitrous oxide were detected). Thus, KPI for nitrate removal ($1000 \text{ g NO}_3^- \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$) was reached. Regarding arsenic dynamics, analyses revealed that full oxidation of arsenite ($> 95 \%$) occurred under the different conditions tested, achieving a maximum arsenite oxidation rate of $94 \pm 6 \text{ gAs(III) m}^{-3} \text{ NAC+NCC d}^{-1}$ in reactor B at the lowest HRT tested ($1.6 \pm 0.1 \text{ h}$).

Figure 2: Fixed-bed reactor with anodic granular graphite

Along this time, graphite granules were regularly taken for electrochemical and microbial characterization. Electrochemical characterization revealed an electrochemical activity linked to nitrate with a formal potential at $-0.02 \pm 0.01 \text{ V}$ vs. SHE at $\text{pH } 7.8 \pm 0.2$. Microbial analyses revealed a cathode predominantly covered by *Sideroxydans lithotrophicus* (71 ± 3 and $52 \pm 3 \%$ sequences), which belongs to *Gallionellaceae* family. Some studies revealed its presence in autotrophic Fe(II)-oxidizing and nitrate-reducing enrichment culture (Shelobolina et al., 2012).

Figure 3: A) Nitrate loading rate and nitrate removal rate under different HRTs and recirculation flowrates. B) Arsenite loading rate and arsenite removal rate under different HRTs and recirculation flowrates.

Along the experimental period, the COVID-19 appeared, which allowed to test the resilience of the system. During COVID-19 lockdown (days 275-322 of reactors operation), influent flow rate was decreased to an HRT of 20 ± 1 h in both reactors to keep a minimum activity. After COVID-19 lockdown, influent flow-rate was increased step-wise to previous flow rates. As shown in Figure 4 for reactor replicate A, the activity of the reactor was recovered to nitrate removal rate values similar to those observed before the COVID-19 lockdown. These results highlight the resilience of the system.

Figure 4: Evolution of current density, nitrate loading rate and nitrate reduction rate after COVID-10 lockdown.

After these tests, synthetic groundwater was changed with softened groundwater from Navata site (nitrate pilot site for WP4). Results obtained were published at Science of Total Environment journal (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150433). Navata’s groundwater contains a high amount of calcium ($> 100 \text{ mgCa}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), which could precipitate on the electrodes surface. For this reason, the treatment of this water at pilot scale considers the usage of a softener. Navata groundwater was firstly softened and then used to feed the BES reactors. By operating the system at $2.1 \pm 0.1 \text{ h}$, nitrate was removed at a rate of $1269 \pm 30 \text{ g NO}_3^- \text{m}^{-3} \text{NCC d}^{-1}$ ($97 \pm 1 \%$ removal) without nitrite nor nitrous oxide accumulation. These tests demonstrated the good performance of the fixed bed BES with real nitrate-polluted groundwater. The fixed bed BES with granular graphite at the anode was selected as one of the designs to be tested at pilot scale in WP4.

BIONISE

Working principle

The BioNISE concept accounts for Bioelectrochemical Nitrogen removal in Secondary effluents. It explores the usage of electroactive nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria to remove ammonium and nitrates from secondary WW (Figure 5). The concept is thought to be a bioelectrochemical upgrade kit for a secondary settler, promoting the enrichment of electroactive nitrifiers and denitrifiers already present in urban wastewater treatment plants. On the anode, nitrifying bacteria converts ammonium into dinitrogen gas, while in the cathode denitrifying bacteria reduce nitrates into N_2 . Being nitrate the most nitrogen available compound expected for a secondary effluent, the cathode is controlled at a poised cathode potential of -320 mV vs. Ag/AgCl (Pous et al., 2015). Since the anodic ammonium removal process is still a mostly unknown process, along ELECTRA project a relevant part of research was focused on better understanding its underlying fundamentals of such a process.

Figure 5: Working principle of the BioNISE technology.

Experimental / testing set-up

Table 2: Experimental set-up for test Unveiling microbial electricity driven anoxic ammonium removal.

Set-up	Unveiling microbial electricity driven anoxic ammonium removal
Purpose of the study	Evaluate the underlying fundamentals of bioelectrochemical ammonium oxidation
Description of the set-up	Two identical rectangular BES. Anode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NAC = 0.40L. Anode/Cathode separator AEM (AMI-7001, Membranes Int., USA). Cathode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NCC = 0.40L. Reference electrode: Ag/AgCl reference electrode (+0.197 V vs. SHE, model RE-5B, BASI, UK). Anode potential poised at +603 mV vs. Ag/AgCl. Each chamber connected to a 2 L tank.
Sampling	Anode and cathode compartment
Analyzed parameters	NH ₄ ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , pH, conductivity (APHA, 2005). N ₂ H ₄ with a colourimetric kit (Spectroquant® Hydrazine test 109,711, Merck, Germany). NH ₂ OH with a colourimetric method (Oshiki et al., 2016). N ₂ O (Micosensor Unisense, Denmark). Dissolved O ₂ (model 6050, detection limit 0.1 mg O ₂ L ⁻¹ , Mettler Toledo, USA)
Other observed parameters	Microbiological analysis: Anode and cathode granules and bulk liquid analysis by Illumina MiSeq.

Table 3: Experimental set-up for test Electricity-driven anoxic ammonium removal under continuous-flow mode.

Set-up	Electricity-driven anoxic ammonium removal under continuous-flow mode
Purpose of the study	Evaluate whether the performance of bioelectrochemical ammonium oxidation under continuous-flow mode
Description of the set-up	Two identical tubular BES. Anode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NAC = 0.30L. Anode/Cathode separator tubular CEM (CMI-7000, Membranes Int., USA). Cathode filled with Granular graphite (diameter 1.5-5 mm, enViro-cell, Germany) and graphite rod as electron collector (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain). NCC = 0.15L. Reference electrode: Ag/AgCl sat. KCl reference electrode (+0.197 V vs. SHE, SE 11, Xylem Analytics Germany). Anode potential poised at +603 mV vs. Ag/AgCl.
Sampling	Influent and effluent
Analyzed parameters	NH ₄ ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , pH, conductivity (APHA, 2005).
Other observed parameters	-

Table 4: Experimental set-up for test Bioelectrochemical upgrade kit for WW polishing in secondary settlers.

Set-up	Bioelectrochemical upgrade kit for WW polishing in secondary settlers
Purpose of the study	Evaluate the integration of a bioelectrochemical kit to increase ammonium and nitrate removal in secondary settlers.
Description of the set-up	Two piston flow reactors. Total volume = 0.17 L. Anode: Granular rod (4 x 2500 mm, Mersen Ibérica, Spain) or Ti-MMO rod (4 x 2500 mm, NMT electrodes, South Africa). NAC = 0.15L. Cathode: Graphite coated stainless steel mesh (developed by RCEES). NCC = 0.02L. Reference electrode: Ag/AgCl sat. KCl reference electrode (+0.197 V vs. SHE, SE 11, Xylem Analytics Germany). Current density fixed at different values from 3 to 36 mA.
Sampling	Influent and effluent
Analyzed parameters	NH ₄ ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NO ₂ ⁻ , pH, conductivity (APHA, 2005). COD with a colourimetric kit (LCK314, LCK514, Hach, USA). N ₂ O (Micosensor Unisense, Denmark).
Other observed parameters	

Operation and results

Unveiling microbial electricity driven anoxic ammonium removal

The underlying fundamentals of bioelectrochemical ammonium oxidation were investigated in two rectangular BES for 550 days. Results obtained in these tests were published at Bioresource Technology Reports journal (DOI: 10.1016/j.biteb.2022.100975). A representative batch profile of ammonium removal is shown in Figure 6. Ammonium was removed at a constant rate ($4.8 \text{ mgN} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}_{\text{NAC}} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$), while the current density remained stable ($0.44 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$). NH₄⁺ was removed under anoxic conditions (dissolved O₂ < 0.1 mgO₂·L⁻¹) without a detectable accumulation of nitrification/denitrification intermediates (i.e., NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, N₂O). The tests performed assumed that ammonium was removed via an electricity-driven process in the absence of oxygen. Assuming an oxidation of NH₄⁺ to N₂, an average coulombic efficiency of 108% could be estimated. This suggested that the current flow detected in the system corresponded to approximately 3 electrons per mole of NH₄⁺ oxidized. Different tests with possible nitrogen species intermediates (i.e. NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, NH₂OH) were performed to elucidate these possible reactions.

Figure 6: Representative batch test with ammonium as the main nitrogen source. Time evolution of nitrogen species content (NO_x^- total refers to $\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^-$) and current density after adding NH_4^+ at the anode of reactors A (A, left) and B (B, right).

The role of nitrite was investigated by spikes on the anode and the cathode in presence and absence of ammonium. Nitrite was rapidly consumed in all tests together with the observation of an oxidative current density peak (up to $10 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and a transient nitrate accumulation that ended with a final conversion to N_2 . The nitrite removal rates ($41.7 - 87.4 \text{ mg N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}_{\text{NAC}}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$) were much higher than the observed ammonium removal rates. This indicated that any nitrite generated from ammonium oxidation was rapidly removed from the reactor, avoiding any detectable nitrite accumulation. The role of nitrate was explored following a similar procedure than nitrite. In this case, the presence of nitrate implied a current depletion ($0.12 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ on average). When nitrate was fully removed, the current density rose again to its previous levels ($0.47 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$). It suggested a plug-unplug mechanism, with current being interrupted by the presence of nitrate and restored after NO_3^- had been removed completely. Electricity-driven nitrate removal was discarded since the number of electrons transferred from the anode to the cathode could only account for 2% of the nitrate removal. Finally, the role of hydroxylamine was evaluated by spiking the compound to the anode. NH_2OH spike caused an increase of the current density that peaked at $90.6 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ (a value higher than the observed for nitrite) and a removal rate of $1082.7 \text{ mg N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}_{\text{NAC}}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ was observed with nitrite nor nitrate generation. Considering that abiotic tests presented an oxidation of hydroxylamine to nitrate, these results suggests a biotic mechanism ruling NH_2OH oxidation to N_2 in the BES.

Samples from the bulk liquid and the biofilm were collected and the microbial community was analyzed. Most sequences belonged to the phylum *Proteobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes* and *Chloroflexi*. Some differences between anode-cathode and bulk-biofilm were observed at lower taxonomic tanks. For example, *Achromobacter* sp. dominated in the anode biofilms (50 – 60 % relative abundance), but it was found at lower levels in the cathode (13 – 26 %). *Achromobacter* species have been related to heterotrophic heterotrophic nitrification (Ahamed Basha et al., 2018), a process that has been more deeply studied with *Alcaligenes* sp. (Wu et al., 2021). *Alcaligenes* presents a novel oxidase that can oxidize hydroxylamine directly to N_2 . Hence, it cannot be discarded a similar role of such a mechanism in *Achromobacter*. Denitrifiers were also detected in

the systems (e.g. *Denitrisonoma*) with higher abundances in the cathode (10 %) than in the anode (4 %). Conventional nitrifiers such as *Nitrosomonas* sp. or *Nitrospira* sp. were found at low abundances (< 6 %). In a similar manner ANAMMOX were found at levels < 2% (e.g. “Candidatus *Kuenenia*” (Brocadiales) and “Candidatus *Anammoximicrobium*”).

Taking all results together, experiments performed with the sole presence of ammonium resulted in a full conversion to N_2 and with current densities corresponding to the use of 3 electrons per molecule of NH_4^+ oxidation to N_2 (i.e., theoretical value). Two highly electroactive reactions were identified (hydroxylamine and nitrite oxidation). Data obtained from nitrite and nitrate tests suggested that both denitrification and ANAMMOX based reactions could take place in the BES to close the conversion of NH_4^+ into N_2 . In fact, the dominant bacteria in the BES was a nitrifier (*Achromobacter* spp.), but the microbial community in the reactor included also ANAMMOX species (*Candidatus Kuenenia* and *Candidatus Anammoximicrobium*) and denitrifying bacteria (*Denitratisoma* sp.). The system studied here presented a complex microbial community that was able to carry out a plethora of nitrogen removal mechanisms. From a black-box perspective, the system was able to handle different nitrogen compounds that are usually present in wastewater (i.e. ammonium, nitrite and nitrate) and convert them into dinitrogen gas without the presence of organic matter.

Electricity-driven anoxic ammonium removal under continuous-flow mode

Two tubular fixed-bed BES reactors (replicates A and B) were assembled and operated to treat the nitrogen content in secondary wastewater (Figure 7). Reactors were inoculated with the effluent of previous reactors that were able to convert ammonium into dinitrogen gas in an anaerobic anode (see “Unveiling microbial electricity driven anoxic ammonium removal”). Reactors were tested using both synthetic wastewater and real secondary wastewater (Quart WWTP, Spain). Results obtained indicated the removal of ammonium at rates ranging between 20 and 40 $gN \cdot m^{-3}_{NAC} \cdot d^{-1}$ and presenting total nitrogen removal rates between 20 and 60 $gN \cdot m^{-3}_{NAC} \cdot d^{-1}$ (Figure 8), being significantly higher than those observed under batch mode (see “Unveiling microbial electricity driven anoxic ammonium removal”).

Figure 7: A) Schematics of the tubular fixed-bed BES reactor for nitrogen removal. B) Photo of the tubular fixed-bed BES reactor for nitrogen removal in secondary wastewaters.

A)

HRT	1.0 d	0.5 d	0.5 d	0.5 d
Anode potential (vs. SHE)	+0.8 V	+0.8 V	+0.3 V	+0.3 V
Wastewater	Synthetic	Synthetic	Synthetic	Real

B)

HRT	1.0 d	0.5 d	0.5 d	0.5 d
Anode potential (vs. SHE)	+0.8 V	+0.8 V	+0.3 V	+0.3 V
Wastewater	Synthetic	Synthetic	Synthetic	Real

Figure 8: A) Evolution of nitrogen concentrations and current. B) Evolution of ammonium and total nitrogen removal rate.

Bioelectrochemical upgrade kit for WW polishing in secondary settlers

In order to bring BES-based nitrogen removal closer to their application secondary effluents, an alternative reactor design was developed to introduce an electrochemical upgrade to currently running secondary settlers (Bioelectrochemical Nitrogen removal in Secondary Settlers - BioNiSe) (Figure 9). Two lab-scale reactor replicates were assembled as explained above (Table 31), inoculated with denitrifying bacteria (Ceballos-Escalera et al., 2021) and fed with secondary wastewater (Quart WWTP, Spain). Reactors were equipped with stainless-steel mesh covered with graphite used as cathode (developed by the Chinese partner RCEES). Tests were performed in collaboration with UNIBO (Mr. Alberto Botti research stay). Results obtained were published in Chemical Engineering journal (DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2022.138949).

A)

B)

Figure 9: A) Schematics of the Bioelectrochemical upgrade kit reactor. B) Photo of the two reactor replicates.

Initial testing under continuous-flow mode conditions was performed with real secondary wastewater scarce in ammonium ($0 - 8.9 \text{ mg N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and a high content of nitrates ($18.7 - 31.5 \text{ mgN}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (NH_4^+ -scarce) (Figure 10). The HRT of the system was reduced over time from $7.4 \pm 0.6 \text{ h}$ to $2.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ h}$. Total nitrogen removal rate increased from $94 \pm 17 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}_{\text{TCV}} \text{ d}^{-1}$ to $156 \pm 60 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}_{\text{TCV}} \text{ d}^{-1}$. Under the different conditions the total nitrogen content at the effluent (between 2 ± 3 and $4 \pm 3 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}$) was found to be lower than the threshold for water reuse ($< 15 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}$). Ammonium was fully removed, without no nitrite nor nitrous oxide accumulation (Figure 11). Thus, at the end of this experimental phase, the bioelectrochemical upgrade kit demonstrated the ability to simultaneously polish ammonium and nitrate content from secondary wastewater with low ammonium content.

In a second experimental phase, real secondary wastewater enriched with ammonium ($18.0 - 33.7 \text{ mg N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) with also a high content of nitrates ($19.3 - 40.8 \text{ mgN}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (NH_4^+ -enriched), thus implying an improper nitrifying activity in the secondary treatment. Since the systems were already working, the initial HRT tested was $2.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ h}$. A high total nitrogen removal rate of $249 \pm 29 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}_{\text{TCV}} \text{ d}^{-1}$ was observed. However, the effluent composition was found to be above the threshold ($28 \pm 3 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}$), because the reactors were able to remove the influent NO_3^- , but not the whole of the NH_4^+ . At this point anode graphite electrode was replaced by Ti-MMO electrode in order to evaluate not only the removal of nitrogen compounds, but also pathogens through hypochlorite evolution. Under these conditions, total nitrogen removal decreased to a minimum of $164 \pm 50 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}_{\text{TCV}} \text{ d}^{-1}$. Denitrification became less evident at this point, with an effluent nitrate content of $21 \pm 13 \text{ mgN L}^{-1}$ compared to $20 \pm 2 \text{ mg N L}^{-1}$ in the influent, while ammonium was still clearly reduced, going from 23 ± 3 to $6 \pm 7 \text{ mgN-NH}_4^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively in the influents and effluents. When the inlet is pumped to the reactors, denitrification takes place at the cathode, converting NO_3^- to N_2 . Subsequently NH_4^+ nitrification is likely to be stimulated anodically, thanks to the electrochemical oxygen produced (Lai et al., 2015), thus restoring the nitrate content. If ammonium content was low or the working HRT was high, nitrate content of the effluent was either negligible or it could still be cathodically reduced thanks to back-diffusion, as observed during the initial experimental phase. However, at higher ammonium concentrations, the reactors were not able to completely remove total nitrogen, but stimulate ammonium conversion to nitrate.

After having assessed the nitrogen removal abilities of the reactors, wastewater was changed again to NH_4^+ -scarce medium and the electricity supply was switched off to identify the effect of the current on the microbial activities (OCV test). Without electrical stimulation, TN removal rate dropped to $113 \pm 23 \text{ gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}_{\text{TCV}}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ (Figure 10), a value between 1.5 and 2 times lower than the ones observed with electricity supply.

Figure 10: Inlet flows and removal rates of bioelectrochemical upgrade kit reactors at the different tested conditions.

Legend: TN_IN = Total nitrogen influent rate; TN_RR = Total nitrogen removal rate. Dashed blue line = Nitrate enriched WW. Dashed brown line = Ammonium enriched WW. Dashed green line = OCV test.

Figure 11: Influent and effluent compositions of bioelectrochemical upgrade kit reactors at the different tested conditions.

Legend: IN = Influent rate; EFF = Effluent. Dashed blue line = Nitrate enriched WW. Dashed brown line = Ammonium enriched WW. Dashed green line = OCV test.

In parallel to nitrogen removal, emerging compounds and pathogens removal were evaluated. At the date of this first report of results, the results concerning emerging compounds are not available yet. Regarding the pathogens removal, the total coliforms (TC) content of WW was characterized, reporting an influent concentration $>2 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$. The reactors equipped with graphite anodes showed a similar removal of the total coliforms content compared to the open circuit condition, resulting in an average effluent concentration of $1.3 \pm 0.9 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$ and $1.3 \pm 0.4 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$ for the graphite and the open circuit tests, respectively. Instead, reactors integrated with Ti-MMO anodes reduced the total coliforms to $0.4 \pm 0.1 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$. The better result obtained with the metal anode is likely to be due to the higher anodic stability, that favours the formation of oxidant agents rather than the oxidation of the anodic material itself (Hand and Cusick, 2021). Thus, titanium coated anode appeared to be the best option for an efficient water polishing, considering that in the perspective of water reuse the law requirements can be very stricter in terms of pathogens content. For instance, the limit for urban uses in Greece and Spain ranges respectively from 0.3 to $1.3 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$ of TC and absence to $2 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$ of *E. coli* (Ilias et al., 2014; Pous et al., 2021). Whereas the more stringent Italian law requires a maximum threshold of $1 \log(\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1})$ of *E. coli* independently from the reuse applications (M.D. 185/2003, 2003).